

**IN RICE (ORIZA SATIVA) VARIETIES THE PLANT GROWS AT
DIFFERENT WATER THICKNESSES, WATER CONSUMPTION DURING
DEVELOPMENT PERIODS, M³**

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Abstract. In this article, 3 rice varieties of early ripening "Guljahon", medium ripening "Iskandar" and late ripening "Lazurniy" rice (oriza sativa) have different water thickness of 5, 10 and 15 cm during the growing season, m³.

Key words. Rice, varieties. mode, rail, development period, water, consumption, m³.

Introduction. Since the cultivation of rice by man, the conditions for its water supply have varied in different parts of the world, because the climatic and soil conditions of the regions of the globe are different, and rice is grown under these conditions. There are no shortages of rice water supply in the East and South Asian countries of the world, where most rice is grown, as the climate of these regions is rich in natural precipitation and in many cases it is necessary to temporarily protect rice from water.

In his Address to the Oliy Majlis on January 24, 2020, President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev expressed his views on continuing research and development to increase the interest of farmers in agriculture and the introduction of advanced technologies and cluster systems in the sector. In his address, the President also spoke about the efficient use of water resources, in particular: "In 2020, we will introduce water-saving technologies on 44,000 hectares of land, or almost four times more than last year. For this purpose, 300 billion soums will be allocated from the state budget. It is also necessary to automate the management of water facilities, water control and accounting systems. It is obvious that the President pays great attention to agriculture [1].

Water shortages are threatening the North China Plain. It is necessary to develop an irrigation strategy to save water.

Here it is necessary to solve the problem of water scarcity through scientific research on the cultivation of aerobic rice with low water consumption. Chinese scientists have conducted extensive research on advanced technologies for growing rice in water-scarce conditions in the region [8; 9; 10 websites].

The degree to which the problem has been studied. The results of research conducted by the authors A.P.Djulay (1968), U.Orolboev (1993), M.I.Uklonskaya (1934) differ from other agricultural crops in the ability of rice to grow and develop in water. Without a lot of water, rice will not produce high yields. Rice grows hygrophyte, ie under water, but the demand for water varies depending on the period of development. Rice does not need water thickness during mowing and is the same during wax ripening and full ripening. Water is needed for the seed to germinate, but the thickness of the water in the soil can only lead to the development of buds, but the roots do not develop, so after sowing the seeds are drained from the field until germination (up to 1 leaf). After the rice sprouts, the thickness of the water rises to 15-20 cm. For better development of the root system and side branches, the thickness of the water during the accumulation period is reduced until it is absorbed, but should not dry out. During this period, fertilizer is fed, and then again the thickness of the water rises to 15-20 cm plant height until the period of wax ripening. [2; 285-287-p], [3; 7-p], [4; 60-69-p].

The purpose of the study. The study consists of studying the effect of water consumption, m³, of different water thicknesses of 5, 10 and 15 cm during the growing season on 3 rice varieties Guljahon, middle Iskandar and late Lazurniy (oriza sativa).

Research methods. "Methods of conducting field experiments." Conducted on the basis of methodological manuals such as "Methodology of field experiments" (BA Dospekhov, 1985) and "Methodological guidelines for water conservation in rice cultivation in Uzbekistan (2019)" [5; 6; 7].

Soil and climatic conditions of the study area. The research was conducted in the experimental fields of the Rice Research Institute. The Rice Research Institute is located in the south-eastern part of the Tashkent region, in the Chirchik oasis, 15 km from Tashkent, on the left bank of the Chirchik River. Geographically, the coordinates of the institute are limited to 69°18' on the Greenwich scale, east longitude and 41°20' north latitude. The relief of the experimental farm is flat, the soil in the experimental fields corresponds to the soil along the river, the soil layer of the area consists of meadow and meadow-

swamp soil. Layers of different depths are composed of sand, large and small stones. The emergence of this type of soil is mainly explained by the fact that the lands attached to the institute are located close to the banks of the Chirchik River, the surrounding farms are engaged in rice cultivation and there is a lot of moisture in the soil.

The plowing layer of the experimental area is a layer of sand and small stones at a depth of 60-70 cm from the surface of the soil 35-40 cm. The sandy and fine-grained layer is also found at Map 9 of the experimental area at 5-10 cm and in some places at 30-40 cm. The soil in the central experimental farm is unsalted, RN-6,8-7,3, heavy sandy soil in terms of mechanical composition. The amount of physical mud in the plowing layer is 45-60%. Groundwater is not mineralized due to the fact that the lower layer of the soil consists of rocks and gravel, the experimental farm area is partly sloping (0.0034-0.0040), groundwater (northeast, southwest) moves up and down. In recent years, in the Chirchik oasis, there has been a strong filtration due to the movement of groundwater (especially to the experimental farm area) due to the discharge of wastewater into ditches and the sand and gravel of the soil layer. Each year, before planting rice, samples were taken diagonally to evaluate the experimental area, the soil from 5 points of the plowing layer from an agronomic point of view, and to determine the bulk density of the soil. Soil density was determined by the cylindrical method.

All soil samples obtained and their preparation were carried out in accordance with the All-Union RSRI manual, (Savvinov.N.I. 1963). To determine the moving appearance of nutrients [NPK]. Before planting, samples were taken diagonally from the experimental area at a depth of 5–20 cm with a burr. Ammonia nitrogen was determined using Nessler's reagent, mobile phosphorus by B.P.Machigin method, (M., Kolos) on a general potassium flame photometer, and humus by I.V.Tyurin method (M., Kolos).

Soil samples were taken before planting to determine the general and mobile form of humus, nitrogen, phosphorus, and potassium in the soil. The amount of humus in the plowing thickness of the experimental field is 1.8-1.9%, total nitrogen is 0.22-0.2%, phosphorus is 0.17-0.18%, potassium is 0.7-0.8%. When the results obtained from soil samples in the experimental field were analyzed, it was found that the amount of potassium in the soil was higher than the mobile form of the nutrients required for the plant.

Research results. The experimental rice varieties were planted on May 12 at the lysometric experimental site of the Rice Research Institute. Studies have

shown that different water thicknesses of 5, 10, and 15 cm at different water thicknesses dramatically affect the developmental phases of rice plants, Full ripening in 5 cm of water is 108 days in “Guljahon” variety, 119 days in “Iskandar” variety and 122 days in “Lazurniy” variety, 110 days in Guljahon variety, 119 days in Iskandar variety and 123 days in Lazurniy variety with 10 cm water thickness, and 115days in Guljahon variety, days in Iskandar variety, 123 days in Lazurniy variety and 132 days in Lazurniy variety (Table 1).

Experiments also revealed water consumption of different water thicknesses during plant growth and development. At the same time, the water consumption during the whole growing period of rice is 13498 m³ in “Guljahon” variety, 16111 m³ in “Iskandar” variety, 15327 m³ in “Lazurniy” variety when the water thickness is 5 cm, When the water thickness is 10 cm, 19453 m³ in “Guljahon” variety, 19040 m³ in “Iskandar” variety, 18136 m³ in Lazurniy variety, When the water thickness was 10 5 cm, it was 22110 m³ in “Guljahon” variety, 21348 m³ in “Iskandar” variety, 20184 m³ in “Lazurniy” variety (Table 1).

Table 1

Water consumption during plant growth and development periods of different water thickness, m³

No	Water thickness c m	Sproutin gg	Mowing	tillering	Tubing	Germina tion	Flowerin gg	Milking	Ripening period
“Guljahon” type									
1	5	1270	794	5717	1112	1429	1112	2064	13498
2	10	1636	1454	7454	2182	1818	1818	3091	19453
3	15	2010	1809	8442	2412	2010	1809	3618	22110
“Iskandar” type									
5	5	1239	1377	6747	1652	1377	1377	2341	16111
6	10	1600	1440	8000	1920	1600	1440	3040	19040
7	15	1779	1779	8183	2135	1779	2313	3380	21348
“Lazurniy” type									
9	5	1179	1310	6419	1572	1310	1179	2358	15327
10	10	1372	1524	7315	1829	1524	1676	2896	18136
11	15	1682	1682	7905	2018	1682	2018	3196	20184

Conclusions. From the above data, it can be concluded that research was conducted on early-ripening varieties "Guljahon", middle-ripening "Iskandar", late-ripening "Lazurniy". At the same time, water consumption during the whole growing season of rice was 13498 m³ in "Guljahon" variety, 16111 m³ in "Iskandar" variety, 15327 m³ in "Lazurniy" variety when the water thickness was 5 cm. When the water thickness is 10 cm, 19453 m³ in "Guljahon" variety, 19040 m³ in "Iskandar" variety, 18136 m³ in "Lazurniy" variety, When the water thickness was 10 5 cm, it was found that it was 22110 m³ in "Guljahon" variety, 21348 m³ in "Iskandar" variety, 20184 m³ in "Lazurniy" variety.

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